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Similar prevalence of long-term post-COVID symptoms in patients with asthma: A case-control study

Dear Editor,

The severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) disproportionately impacts people with some pre-existing medical comorbidities, e.g., diabetes, hypertension or cardiovascular conditions. For instance, hypertensive patients exhibit higher mortality risk than normotensive patients with SARS-CoV-2 infection.¹ Asthma is another medical comorbidity which could influence the course of COVID-19. Interestingly, asthma seems to be a “protective factor”, since the risk of presenting severe COVID-19 in people with asthma is small;² although a recent meta-analysis concluded that pre-existing asthma was a predictor of intubation particularly just in young and obese COVID-19 patients.³

Current evidence supports the presence of long-COVID, that is, individuals who have recovered from COVID-19 but exhibit symptoms after the acute phase far longer than it would be expected.⁴ In a letter to the editor in *Journal of Infection*, Garrigues et al. analysed the presence of post-COVID symptoms in hospitalized patients and found that the most prevalent persistent symptoms were fatigue, dyspnoea, and loss of memory.⁵ Very recently, Moreno-Perez et al. observed that 59% of hospitalized and 37% of non-hospitalized patients exhibited post-COVID symptoms 3 months after the infection.⁶ In a posterior letter to the editor in *Journal of Infection*, Garcia-Pachon et al. described a series of patients with asthma showing low prevalence of symptoms 3 months after infection.⁷ However, this study did not include a comparison control group including COVID-19 patients without asthma. We present the first case-control study comparing the differences in post-COVID symptoms between hospitalized patients with and without asthma.

From all patients admitted to Hospital Universitario Infanta Leonor-Virgen de la Torre and Hospital Universidad Fundación Alcorcón (Madrid, Spain) with a diagnosis of SARS-CoV-2 by RT-PCR technique during the first wave of the pandemic (March 10th to May 31st, 2020), a randomized sample of 400 patients from each hospital was selected. From those selected, patients with asthma prior to hospitalization were included as cases. Additionally, age-

Table 1. Demographic, hospitalisation data, and post-COVID symptoms of COVID-19 patients with and without pre-existing asthma.

	Asthmatic (n = 61)	Non-asthmatic (n = 122)
Age, mean (SD), years	55 (17)	55 (16.5)
Gender, male/female (%)	15 (24.6%) / 46 (75.4%)	30 (24.6%) / 92 (75.4%)
Weight, mean (SD), kg.*	79.5 (23)	77.0 (15.5)
Height, mean (SD), cm.	164 (11)	163 (9)
Body Mass Index, mean (SD), kg/cm²*	29.8 (9.5)	29.0 (4.5)
Smoking status, n (%)		
Active	4 (6.6%)	9 (7.3%)
None or Former	57 (93.4%)	112 (92.7%)
Medical co-morbidities		
Asthma Treatment	61 (100%)	0 (0.0%)
Hypertension	13 (18.9%)	28 (22.9%)
Cardiovascular Disease	4 (6.5%)	10 (8.2%)
Diabetes*	1 (1.6%)	10 (8.2%)
Obesity	2 (3.3%)	7 (5.7%)
Rheumatological Disease	1 (1.6%)	4 (3.3%)
Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease	3 (4.9%)	5 (4.1%)
Migraine	3 (4.9%)	3 (2.4%)
Other (Cancer, Kidney Disease)	9 (14.7%)	23 (18.8%)
Symptoms at hospital admission, n (%)		
Fever	38 (62.3%)	90 (73.7%)
Dyspnoea*	28 (45.9%)	35 (28.6%)
Myalgia*	32 (52.4%)	42 (34.4%)
Cough	21 (34.4%)	35 (28.6%)
Headache	12 (19.7%)	27 (22.1%)
Diarrhoea	11 (18.0%)	24 (19.7%)
Anosmia	6 (9.8%)	13 (10.6%)
Ageusia	4 (6.6%)	8 (6.6%)
Throat Pain	6 (9.8%)	10 (8.2%)
Stay at the hospital, mean (SD), days		
Intensive Care Unit (ICU) admission		
Yes/No, n (%)	7 (11.5%) / 54 (88.5%)	5 (4.1%) / 117 (95.9%)
Stay at ICU, mean (SD), days	18.3 (21.1)	9.4 (8.4)
Number of post-COVID symptoms, n (%)		
None	8 (13.2%)	25 (20.4%)
1 or 2	23 (37.7%)	45 (36.9%)
3 or more	30 (49.1%)	52 (42.7%)
Post-COVID symptoms, n (%)		
Dyspnoea on exertion	46 (75.4%)	71 (58.2%)
Fatigue	40 (65.6%)	75 (61.5%)
Dyspnoea rest	21 (34.4%)	34 (27.8%)
Memory Loss	11 (18.0%)	20 (16.4%)
Skin Rashes	8 (13.1%)	13 (10.6%)
Concentration loss	8 (13.1%)	14 (11.4%)
Cognitive Blunting - Brain fog	6 (9.9%)	10 (8.2%)
Gastrointestinal Disorders - Diarrhoea	2 (3.3%)	5 (4.1%)
Tachycardia-Palpitations	6 (9.8%)	8 (6.5%)
Ocular/Vision Disorders	4 (6.6%)	9 (7.3%)
Ageusia/Hypogeusia	1 (1.6%)	3 (2.5%)
Anosmia/Hyposmia	4 (6.6%)	2 (1.6%)
Throat Pain	2 (3.3%)	3 (2.5%)
HADS-D (0–21), mean (SD)*	6.1 (5.6)	5.4 (4.9)
Depressive Symptoms (HADS-D ≥ 10 points), n (%)	17 (27.9%)	27 (22.1%)
HADS-A (0–21), mean (SD)*	5.5 (5.5)	5.3 (4.8)
Anxiety Symptoms (HADS-A ≥ 12 points), n (%)	9 (14.75%)	14 (11.5%)
PSQJ (0–21), mean (SD)*	8.8 (4.6)	7.5 (4.3)
Poor Sleep Quality (PSQJ ≥ 8 points), n (%)*	33 (54.1%)	51 (41.8%)

HADS: Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (A: Anxiety; D: Depression); PSQJ: Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index; SD: Standard Deviation.

* Significant differences between asthmatic and non-asthmatic patients ($P < 0.01$).

and sex-matched hospitalized COVID-19 patients without pre-existing asthma were recruited as controls. Asthma was classified according to the 2019 Global Initiative for Asthma (GINA) guidelines (www.ginasthma.org/). The study was approved by both local Ethics Committees (HUIL/092–20, HUF/EC1517). Participants provided informed consent before collecting data.

Clinical and hospitalization data were collected from hospital records. Participants were scheduled for a telephonic interview by trained healthcare professionals around 7.5 months (SD 0.5) after hospital discharge. Patients were asked to report the presence of symptoms after hospitalization, and if these symptoms

persisted at the time of the study. Participants were systematically asked about a predefined list of post-COVID symptoms including fatigue, dyspnoea at rest, dyspnoea on exertion, chest pain, headache, anosmia, ageusia, cough, palpitations, diarrhoea, cognitive blunting/brain fog, or memory loss, but they were free to report any further symptom that they considered relevant.

The Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS) and the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQJ) were used to assess anxiety/depression symptoms and sleep quality, respectively, as both can be adequately administered by telephone.⁸ We considered cutoff scores considered on the Spanish population for determin-

ing the presence of anxiety (HADS-A $\geq$ 12/21 points) and depressive (HADS-D $\geq$ 10/21 points) symptoms and poor sleep quality (PSQI $\geq$ 8/21 points).⁹

The statistical analysis was conducted with STATA 16.1 (StataCorp. 2019, USA). The McNemar and paired Student t-tests were applied to compare proportions and means between groups. Multivariable conditional logistic regression models were constructed to identify variables associated to the presence of pre-existing asthma. Adjusted odd ratios (OR) or Incident Rate Ratios (IRR) with their 95% confidence intervals (95%CI) were calculated.

From 800 randomized COVID-19 patients hospitalized during the first wave of the pandemic, 61 patients with asthma and 122 age- and sex-matched patients without asthma were recruited. A greater proportion of patients with asthma experienced dyspnoea and myalgia as onset symptoms at hospital admission ($P < 0.05$, **Table 1**). Higher number of patients with asthma also presented diabetes as comorbid condition when compared with those without asthma ($P = 0.045$).

From the total sample, just 34 (18.6%) were completely free of any post-COVID symptom 7 months after hospital discharge. Individuals with pre-existing asthma showed similar (IRR1.07, 95%CI 0.87–1.33, $P = 0.476$) number of post-COVID symptoms (mean: 2.4, SD: 1.4) than those without asthma (mean: 2.2, SD: 1.6). The most prevalent post-COVID symptoms were dyspnoea on exertion, fatigue, and dyspnoea at rest (**Table 1**). In fact, a greater proportion of patients with pre-existing asthma reported dyspnoea on exertion (OR2.73; 95%CI 1.23–6.08; $P = 0.013$) than those without asthma. No differences in the presence of fatigue (OR1.23; 95%CI 0.61–2.49; $P = 0.556$), dyspnoea at rest (OR1.38; 95%CI 0.70–2.75; $P = 0.347$), depressive symptoms (OR1.39, 95%CI 0.67–2.89), anxiety symptoms (OR1.32, 95%CI 0.55–3.18) or poor sleep quality (OR1.71, 95%CI 0.89–3.27, $P = 0.105$) between patients with or without asthma were observed (**Table 1**).

Identification of the phenotype of patients at a higher risk of death during the acute infection or a higher risk of developing post-COVID symptoms is crucial. In our sample, the presence of long-term post-COVID symptoms was similar between patients with and without pre-existing asthma, suggesting that asthma seems not to be a risk factor for more severe long-term post-COVID symptoms but either was a “protective” factor for that. Our results are contrary to those found by Garcia-Pachon et al. in their letter to the Editor.⁷ It should be considered that Garcia-Pachon et al. did not include a “control” group without asthma and also included a shorter follow-up.⁷ Additionally, these authors included non-hospitalized patients, which could explain the discrepancies. Fatigue and dyspnoea were the most common post-COVID symptoms in agreement with current literature,^{5,6} but the presence of dyspnoea with exertion was more frequent in patients suffering from asthma. Distinction between dyspnoea at rest and on exertion maybe crucial in these patients.

Our study has limitations. First, the prevalence of asthma in our sample was 7.6%, in agreement with a meta-analysis reporting a pooled prevalence of asthma in COVID-19 patients of 7.46% (95%CI 6.25–8.67);¹⁰ however, this sample could be considered small. Second, we conducted the follow-up by telephone. Third, just hospitalized patients were included. Fourth, we did not collect objective measures of COVID-19 disease such as inflammatory biomarkers. Finally, we collected data cross-sectionally; therefore, future longitudinal studies are needed.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest

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Reactogenicity, safety and antibody response, after one and two doses of mRNA-1273 in seronegative and seropositive healthcare workers

Dear Editor,

We read with great interest the prospective SARS-CoV-2 sero-
 surveillance study of Harris et al. in your columns.¹ During 6
 months and before the UK vaccination campaign, they followed
 the antibody response in a cohort of 2246 healthcare work-
 ers (HCWs). They relied on 4 commercial kits and an in-house
 test to track the antibody response to natural SARS-CoV-2 expo-
 sure. As expected with kits that targets different proteins and to-
 tal or specific immunoglobulin sub-groups, they observed, along
 time, fluctuating seropositivity from one test to another. Neverthe-
 less, they showed that SARS-CoV-2 antibodies do not decline as
 quickly as predicted by smaller cohorts of patients with shorter
 follow-up.

With the start of worldwide vaccination campaigns, scattered
 evidence is emerging from the medical literature to dispute the
 second injection of mRNA vaccines in individuals previously in-
 fected with SARS-CoV-2.^{2,3} Knowing that a significant proportion
 of the population would be seropositive at the time of the first
 injection, we wanted to investigate the utility of a second dose
 under both supply and time constraints. Here we report our ob-
 servations in a cohort of healthcare workers (HCWs) who were
 administered mRNA1273 at the inception of the national vac-
 cination campaign. Manisty et al., first questioned the admin-
 istration of the second dose of BNT162b2, another mRNA vac-
 cine, so as to reserve it only for individuals not previously in-
 fected.³ They showed that the antibody response after a first
 dose in HCWs previously infected ($n=24$) reached levels 140
 times higher than their peak value before vaccination. Kram-
 mer et al. observed in previously infected individuals antibody
 titers 10–45 times higher than in their uninfected counterparts
 after a first-dose of either BNT162b2 ($n=88$) or mRNA-1273
 ($n=22$) vaccines².

In our prospective study, we compared not only the antibody
 response (Fig. 1) but also the local and systemic side effects in
 terms of duration and intensity after the first and second dose of
 mRNA-1273 (Fig. 2). The quantitative analysis of the anti-SARS-CoV-

2 IgG antibodies directed against the subunits (S1) and (S2) of the
 virus spike protein was carried out using the LIAISON®SARS-CoV-2
 IgG kit (DiaSorin®, Saluggia, Italy) on a LIAISON®XL analyzer pre-
 viously validated in our laboratory.⁴ In order to assess the sero-
 logical status of the participants ($n=160$), a first dosage was car-
 ried out with a median time ($\pm$ 95% confidence interval [CI]) of 2
 ($\pm$ 0.29) days before the first injection (T0). Among those, 36 par-
 ticipants were found to be seropositive. Two other samples were
 taken from all participants 2 weeks after the first injection (T1)
 (median time [$\pm$ 95% CI]: 16 [$\pm$ 0.25] days), and 2 weeks after the
 second injection (T2) (median time [$\pm$ 95% CI]: 14 [$\pm$ 0.21] days).
 Except for 2 individuals, all participants who were seropositive at
 T0, saw their antibody levels boosted by the first dose but no ad-
 ditional boosting effect was observed after the second injection. In
 these two individuals (1.6%), the second injection made it possible
 to raise their antibody levels from 59.7 and 105 AU/mL to above
 the maximum detection limit ($>$ 400 AU/mL) at T2. In seronegative
 participants, the anti-S antibody titers obtained after a single dose
 were comparable to those obtained in unvaccinated seropositive
 participants while the second injection was necessary to achieve
 higher antibody levels approaching those obtained for seropositive
 individuals (T1). We also explored the frequency of side effects af-
 ter the first dose in a slightly larger cohort ($n=206$, mean age,
 48.6 ($\pm$ 11.6) years) including 151 seronegative (71% female) and
 55 seropositive participants (69% female), as well as after the sec-
 ond dose in 113 participants (mean age, 49.2 ($\pm$ 11.3) years) includ-
 ing 89 seronegative participants (69% female) and 24 seropositive
 participants (58% female). The intensity of local and systemic side
 effects reported by participants was graded into 4 levels of sever-
 ity: (very mild, mild, moderate, severe). Common side effects such
 as articular pain, muscular pain, headache, fatigue, fever, adenopa-
 thy and oedema from the first dose appear to be more frequent
 and severe in previously infected individuals ($P < .05$). Neverthe-
 less, it seems that the second injection generates a greater over-
 all systemic reaction than that observed after the first one, re-
 gardless of the initial serological status of the participants. Seven
 days after the first or the second dose, all observed side effects
 disappeared in all participants and none were hospitalized. Two
 weeks after the last injection, a clinical follow-up questionnaire
 was sent to the 113 participants. Only 41 were returned at the time
 of redaction. None of the respondents reported thinking they had
 been infected. Ten of them had to undergo a RT-qPCR and all were
 negative.

Our results plead, in a supply-limited environment, for reserv-
 ing the second dose scheme to seronegative individuals prior to
 vaccination, especially when the serological status is easily ac-
 cessible, as the additional protective effect of the second dose
 has yet to be demonstrated in seropositive individuals. The de-
 termination of the antibody titers after the initial dose could be
 used in order to catch-up the very few vaccinees with a weaker
 response.

In the worrying context of an increase in the spread of
 mutant viruses around the world⁵ and given that most reg-
 istered vaccine platforms use the two-dose-prime boost ap-
 proach,^{6–8} this strategy would help speed up vaccination cam-
 paigns and achieve group immunization goals more rapidly. Even
 though titers of antibodies against S1 spike protein seem to
 correlate with viral neutralization studies,^{6,9,10} only long-term
 serosurveillance studies will not only confirm the results of
 our investigation but will also determine the IgG protection
 thresholds.